

Studies in the Acenaphthenequinone Series.

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The present investigation is a continuation of the work of Sircar and Guha Roy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1048 ; 1929, 6, 93) and undertaken with the object of making a further and thorough study of the various reactions of acenaphthenequinone which are comparable to those of phenanthraquinone.

Sircar and Guha Roy (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1048) have already shown that contrary to the conclusions of Japp and his co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1882, 41, 146), the same aldehyde can be made to react with phenanthraquinone in presence of ammonia under different experimental conditions of temperature and pressure to yield either an oxazole or an iminazole.

Though Sircar and Guha Roy (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 93) prepared a number of oxazoles and iminazoles by the condensation of aromatic aldehydes with acenaphthenequinone in presence of ammonia, they failed to prepare both oxazole and iminazole by the action of the same aldehyde on acenaphthenequinone.

The authors have now found that:—

A. With (1) *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, (2) *p*-acetylamino benzaldehyde, (3) *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, (4) *p*-dimethylamido benzaldehyde and (5) resorcyaldehyde at the ice-cold temperature, only oxazoles are formed, but at higher temperature only iminazoles and no oxazoles are formed.

B. When (1) *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde, (2) salicylaldehyde and (3) *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde are condensed with acenaphthenequinone at the ice-cold temperature in presence of ammonia, invariably a mixture of oxazoles and iminazoles is formed as is evident from their percentage compositions. They cannot however be separated from each other owing to their very little and similar solubilities in most of the organic solvents. But if the reaction is brought about at a higher temperature, then only iminazoles and no oxazoles are obtained.

C. With (1) *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (2) *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and (3) anisylaldehyde even at the ice-cold temperature, only iminazoles and no oxazoles are formed.

D. With (1) vanillin and (2) *p*-bromosalicylaldehyde scarcely any reaction takes place at ice-cold temperature, whereas at higher temperature iminazoles are formed as usual.

From the above results one would be naturally inclined to assume that if the reactions could be carried with the aldehydes under the groups B and C, at a still lower temperature, oxazoles might probably have been obtained without the admixture of any iminazole and probably the oxazoles will be formed at some intermediate temperature with the two aldehydes under the group D, and this still remains to be investigated.

It is interesting to note that only in the case of the *para* substituted aldehydes, if the condensations are effected at a still higher temperature and in a sealed tube, a third and a new type of compound is formed. The percentage of nitrogen in them are almost exactly one and half times of that required by the corresponding iminazoles. They are also deeper in colour than the corresponding iminazoles but nothing definite can be said about their constitution without further study.

The formation of both oxazoles and iminazoles by the condensation of the same aldehyde with acenaphthenequinone in presence of ammonia naturally leads one to suppose that most probably in these reactions oxazoles are first formed which, by subsequent replacement of the oxygen atom of the ring by -NH- group results in the formation of iminazole. Such a replacement is not uncommon, *e.g.*, when pyrones and allied compounds are digested with ammonia, pyridones are formed. (*cf.* Ruhemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 413 ; also Meyer and Oppelt, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 3376).

In order to test how far this supposition is justified an attempt was made to prepare iminazole by heating the corresponding oxazole with ammonia in a sealed tube under pressure. Though the expected iminazole could not be obtained in a pure state in that way, it is interesting to find that the percentage of nitrogen in the resulting product appreciably increased. Evidently at least a partial conversion of the oxazole to iminazole has taken place. Experiments at still higher temperature and pressure are being undertaken by one of us (A.C.S.).

Klinger and Roerdanz (*Annalen*, 1911, 382, 211) studied the

action of sunlight on mixtures of various aldehydes and phenanthraquinone in presence of benzene and obtained interesting addition products of the following type

In a similar way acenaphthenequinone has been condensed in presence of sunlight with (1) salicylaldehyde, (2) cinnamicaldehyde, (3) benzaldehyde and (4) anisaldehyde, and the results obtained are exactly alike to those of Klinger and Roerdanz (*loc. cit.*).

Adopting the method of Japp and Miller (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1885, 47, 11), who were able to condense phenanthraquinone with acetone, monoacetoneacenaphthenequinone has been obtained. The corresponding diacetone derivative could not however be isolated in a sufficiently pure condition.

EXPERIMENTAL.*

2'-Chloro-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole.

Acenaphthenequinone (1 g.) was thoroughly mixed with little more than the molecular proportion of *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde and dissolved in about 90 c.c. of boiling amyl alcohol. Dry ammonia gas was then passed through the hot solution for about two hours and the solution left over night. The separated red precipitate, after being thoroughly washed with ether, was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and toluene as red needles, not melting below 290°.

It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red coloration. It is soluble in nitrobenzene, pyridine or acetic acid, sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone or benzene and insoluble in ether. It dyes wool in light orange shades from an acetic acid bath. (Found: N, 8.9. C₁₉H₁₁N₂ Cl, requires N, 9.27 per cent.).

* Of the oxazoles and iminazoles mentioned in the paper, those that had already been prepared by Sircar and Guha Roy (*loc. cit.*) have not been described.

The acenaphthiminazoles described in Table I were prepared in a similar way and possess properties similar to the preceding compound. The dyeings were made from an acetic acid bath.

TABLE I

Name of product. (P = 2-phenylacenaphth- iminazole)	Formula.	Appearance.	Shade on wool.	Analysis. Found. Calc.
4'-Chloro-P*	$C_{19}H_{11}N_2Cl$	Shining red needles from a mixture of alcohol and toluene.	Pink. N, 9.5	9.27 p.c
3'-Hydroxy-P	$C_{19}H_{12}ON_2$	Shining red needles.	Orange. N, 10.2	9.86 ..
2'-Hydroxy- 4'-bromo-P	$C_{19}H_{11}ON_2Br$	Deep red microcrystalline powder from hot pyridine by cautious addition of hot water.	Yellow ish- orange.	N, 7.9 7.7 ..
3-Nitro-4'-acetyl- amino-P**	$C_{21}H_{14}N_4O_3$	Deep chocolate coloured microcrystalline powder from hot nitrobenzene by precipitation with ether.	Green- ish brown.	N, 14.8 15.13 ..
3:4-Dinitro-4'- acetylamino-P	$C_{21}H_{13}N_5O_5$	Do	Scarlet- red.	N, 16.6 16.86 ..
3-Nitro-4'-chloro-P	$C_{19}H_{10}O_2N_3Cl$	Do	Greyish yellow.	N, 11.80 12.10
3-nitro 4'-hydroxy-3'- methoxy-P	$C_{20}H_{13}O_4N_3$	Dark chocolate coloured powder from hot pyridine by addition of hot water.	Chocolate brown.	N, 11.8 11.69 ..

* This compound had been prepared by Sircar and Guha Roy (*loc. cit.*). They describe it as rose-coloured rectangular plates (from pyridine), melting at 264° with previous shrinking at 242°. Other properties agree.

** The 3 nitro-and 3:4-dinitroacenaphthenequinones used in this investigation were prepared according to the methods of Mayer and Kaufmann (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, 269) and Rowe and Davies (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920. 117, 1347) respectively.

3' : 5'-Dihydroxy-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole.—Through a solution of an intimate mixture of resorcyaldehyde (1 g.) and acenaphthenequinone (1 g.) in 300 c.c. of boiling alcohol, dry ammonia gas was passed for two hours and the mixture allowed to stand for seven days, when a dark chocolate coloured solid gradually separated. This was filtered off and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and alcohol as rectangular plates or prisms.

It is sparingly soluble in alcohol or acetone, moderately soluble in toluene and soluble in acetic acid or pyridine. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colour and a violetish fluorescence. It does not melt below 300°. It dyes wool in yellowish brown shades. (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{19}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.33 per cent.).

4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxy-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole was prepared in a similar way and possesses properties similar to the preceding compound (shining red needles). It dyes wool in pink shades. (Found: N, 8.6. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.92 per cent.).

2'-Nitro-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole.—Acenaphthenequinone (1g.) was thoroughly mixed with nitrobenzaldehyde (1 g.) and heated in a sealed tube with liq. ammonia for about one hour without using any solvent at 80-100°.

The resulting solid was thoroughly washed with ether and finally purified from a mixture of alcohol and benzene. It is a greyish microcrystalline powder, melting at 150° with decomposition.

It is soluble in toluene, benzene, acetic acid or pyridine and insoluble in ether. It dyes wool in brownish-yellow shades. (Found: N, 13.9. $C_{19}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.42 per cent.).

The following two iminazoles were prepared in the same way as and possess properties similar to the preceding compound.

4'-Acetylamino-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole is yellow microcrystalline powder, melts at 255° with decomposition and dyes wool in yellow shades. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{21}H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 12.92 per cent.).

4'-Dimethylamino-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole is deep red microcrystalline powder, melting at 223° with decomposition. It dyes wool in orange brown shades. (Found: N, 13.8. $C_{21}H_{17}N_3$ requires N, 13.5 per cent.).

4'-Hydroxy-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole —Through a solution of an intimate mixture of acenaphthenequinone (1 g.) and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1 g.) in 60 c.c. of boiling amyl alcohol, dry ammonia gas was passed for about 5 minutes, by which time the reaction set

in. The mixture was then cooled by a freezing mixture and the passing of ammonia continued for further two hours, after which the mixture was allowed to stand for 4-5 hours when a light orange coloured solid separated. This was filtered off, washed with ether, and crystallised from acetic acid as red needles not melting below 290° . It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colouration. It is soluble in nitrobenzene, and sparingly soluble in toluene. It dyes wool in light orange shades. (Found: N, 10.0. $C_{19}H_{12}O N_2$, requires N, 9.86 per cent.).

4'-Nitro-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound and obtained as yellow microcrystalline powder (from nitro benzene), melting at 185° with decomposition. It dyes wool in yellow shades. (Found: N, 13.6. $C_{19}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 13.42 per cent.).

4' Chloro-2-phenylacenaphthoxazole.

An intimate mixture of acenaphthenequinone (1 g.) and little more than the molecular quantity of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde was dissolved in boiling amyl alcohol and dry ammonia gas was passed through the hot solution for about 4 minutes. When the reaction had just commenced the mixture was cooled by freezing mixture, ammonia gas was passed for further two hours and then the mixture allowed to stand over night. The light rose-red solid which had separated was filtered off, washed with ether and crystallised from pyridine as rhombic plates mixed with needles, melting at 245° with decomposition. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a light red colouration. It is soluble in nitrobenzene and is sparingly soluble in benzene or toluene. It dyes wool in very light rose shades. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{19}H_{10}ONCl$ requires N, 4.65 per cent.).

4'-Acetylamino-2-phenylacenaphthoxazole was obtained in a similar way as light rose-coloured plates and needles (from pyridine). It is soluble in acetic acid or pyridine, insoluble in ether, acetone or alcohol. It melts at 280° with decomposition. It dyes wool in very light orange shades. (Found: N, 8.2; $C_{21}H_{14}O_2N_2$, requires N, 8.59 per cent.).

Attempt for the conversion of Oxazole to Iminazole.

2'-Nitro-2-phenylacenaphthoxazole was heated in a sealed tube with liquor ammonia for 6 hours in a Carius' furnace (temp. 130°,—above which the tube invariably bursted) and the solid left in the tube crystallised from a mixture of toluene and alcohol. Increase in nitrogen by 0·2 p.c. (in 6 hours), 1·5 p. c. (in 30 hours.) In the case of 4'-acetylamino-2-phenylacenaphthoxazole the increase noted was 2·2 p.c.

Monosalicyloyl derivative of acenaphthenequinol.

A mixture of acenaphthenequinone (2 g.), salicylaldehyde (1·2 c.c.) and benzene (12 c.c.) was introduced in a sealed thin glass tube and exposed to bright sunlight for about a month by which time the colour of the quinone completely changed and a blackish mass was obtained. It was treated with a mixture of alcohol and benzene when a part remained undissolved, and a portion went in solution. The insoluble portion was repeatedly crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and benzene and finally obtained as very light yellow needles.

It melts at 192° with decomposition. It is decomposed when treated with alkali and develops a bluish coloration. (Found: C, 74·6; H, 4·4. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 75·0 ; H, 3·9 per cent.).

The compound yields an acetyl derivative m. p. 248°.

Similar condensation products with other aldehydes are detailed in Table II.

TABLE II.

Aldehyde taken.	Period of exposure to sunlight.	Appearance & M.P.	Analysis Found. Calc.
Cinnamicaldehyde	40 days	Yellowish microcrystalline powder, melting at 246° with decomposition.	C, 79·2 H, 3·9 80·2 p.c. 4·45
Benzaldehyde	15 days	Grey coloured microcrystalline powder, melting at 230° with decomposition.	C, 78·6 H, 3·5 79·16 4·16
Anisaldehyde	20 days	M.P. 193° with decomposition.	C, 74·6 H, 5·0 75·47 4·4

Monoacetoneacenaphthenequinone.

A mixture of acenaphthenquinone (5 g.) and acetone (4.5 g.) was treated with 0.25 c.c. of caustic potash solution (d 1.27) and the mixture thoroughly shaken. A reaction soon set in, the mass blackened with the rise of temperature. After about ten minutes, the black viscous mass was exposed to air, when it changed to a hard solid. This was triturated with ether and kept for about 4-5 hours. The yellowish precipitate was filtered off, the filtrate (A) kept aside. The former was further washed with ether till the ethereal solution was colourless, and repeatedly crystallised from acetone (bright yellow needles). It melts at 252° and its chemical properties respond to those of acenaphthenequinone.

The coloured ethereal solution (A) was treated with animal charcoal and filtered, when the solution became almost colourless. The tarry mass which separated on evaporation of the ether was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether in colourless needles, melting at 117° with decomposition. It is soluble in almost all organic solvents. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 5.3. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0 per cent.).

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